

MAN-MADE CELLULOSE FIBERS COATED WITH CARBON NANOTUBE NETWORKS AS UNIQUE SMART MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Electroconductive man-made cellulose fibers were fabricated by depositing multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) on the surface using a simple and scalable dip coating. The formation of electrically-conducting CNT networks on cellulose mono- and multi-filament fiber surfaces was confirmed by electrical resistance measurements and visualized by scanning electron microscopy. The interaction between CNT networks and cellulose fibers was investigated by Raman spectroscopy. The piezoresistivity of these fibers for strain sensing was investigated. In addition, the sensing behavior of these fibers to liquid (water) and volatile molecules (including vapors of methanol, ethanol, acetone, chloroform and tetrahydrofuran) was investigated. The results revealed a rapid response, high sensitivity, good reproducibility and selectivity for these chemical vapors. It is suggested that the intrinsic physical and chemical features of cellulose fiber, well-formed CNT networks and favorable CNT-cellulose interaction caused the unique and excellent sensing ability of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers, which have the potential to be used as smart materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the development of science and technology, the use of intelligent textiles that are capable of reacting to environmental conditions or stimuli, such as mechanical, thermal, chemical, magnetic or others, is growing in many fields [1,2]. Cellulose-based fibers obtained from natural plants have been used to manufacture fabrics and clothing for millennia. For their unique characteristics, such as being renewable, biocompatible, having good mechanical property, and structural features, such as complicated surface morphology, functional groups, such as hydroxyl groups, and high porosity, which can easily be modified, cellulose fibers have attracted considerable attention [3]. On the other hand, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), which have excellent mechanical, thermal and electrical properties, are considered as one of the most interesting nanoparticles in the technology world today, due to the versatility of their potential applications. Thus, the synergy between a flexible renewable substrate, such as cellulose fibers, and the interesting multifunctionality of CNTs offers a large number of possibilities.

Recently, CNT-functionalized natural cellulose fibers were reported as promising intelligent materials in a variety of applications [4]. In these works, surface modification of cellulose fibers with CNTs was realized by using either covalent or non-covalent modification methods, such as coating/sizing technologies. For instance, CNT network armors were fabricated on the surface of cotton fibers using a simple dip coating method [4]. By using carboxylic acids as crosslinking agents, CNT-coated cotton fabrics were fabricated [5]. These CNT-coated cotton textiles exhibit improved mechanical properties, flame retardancy, ultraviolet-blocking and water-repelling characteristics. Smart yarns and wearable fabrics were developed from cotton threads by using a polyelectrolyte-based coating with CNTs. These materials can be used as wearable biomonitoring and telemedicine sensors, which are simple, sensitive, selective and versatile [6]. Jute fibers and corresponding epoxy-based

composites with sensing abilities could also be realized by depositing multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) on the surfaces of jute fibers or fabrics [7].

In contrast to these natural cellulose fibers mentioned above, the composition and structure of man-made cellulose fibers can be humanly shaped. This lends man-made cellulose fibers special properties and renders them useful for many different purposes. In the present work, we deposited MWCNTs directly onto cellulose fibers through dip coating to fabricate electrically conductive CNT-coated cellulose fibers. The microstructure, mechanical properties and conductive properties of the resultant CNT-cellulose fibers were investigated. Furthermore, their sensing ability to external stimuli was also investigated, including the sensitivity, reproducibility and stability of these fibers as sensors, such as stress/strain sensors, vapor sensors and liquid sensors.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

Cellulose fibers (commercial viscose fibers) with an average diameter of 20 μm were provided by Kelheim Fibers GmbH (Kelheim, Germany). Commercially available MWCNTs (NC3150, Nanocyl S.A., Belgium) with an average diameter of 9.5 nm and an average length of 1.5 μm were used. Organic solvents, non-ionic surfactant Brij76 (polyoxyethylene (10) stearyl ether) and other reagents were of analytical grade and obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2 Preparation of CNT-Coated Cellulose Fibers

The CNT-coated cellulose fibers were prepared according to our previous work [8]. Firstly, a certain amount of MWCNTs was added to a surfactant aqueous solution (Brij76). The ratio of surfactant to CNT was adjusted to 1.5/1 (w/w). The resultant mixture was then sonicated using a horn sonicator for 120 min to give a mixture without visible agglomerates. The dispersions with different CNT contents were thus prepared. Dip coating was then used to apply CNTs onto cellulose-based fibers. For each dipping, fibers were fixed on steel wire frames and immersed in the CNT dispersion for 5 min, following 30 min of drying in air. By varying the number of dipping repetitions and CNT content in dispersions, cellulose fibers coated with different amounts of CNTs were fabricated. In this work, CNT-coated cellulose fibers were prepared using dispersions with 0.5 wt% CNTs three times, if not stated otherwise. All fibers prepared were dried in a vacuum oven at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 8 h before testing.

2.3 Characterization of Morphology and Microstructure

The surface of the MWCNT-coated cellulose fibers was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Ultra 55, Carl Zeiss SMT AG, Germany).

The mechanical properties of the fibers were measured with a FAVIGRAPH semiautomatic equipment (Textechno Company, Germany). The extension rate was set at 20 mm/min. All data were collected under the same conditions: 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 50% relative humidity (RH). The average values were calculated with 50 specimens for each fiber.

The electrical resistance of the single MWNT-cellulose fibers was measured with a Keithley 2001 electrometer (Keithley Instruments GmbH, Germany) at 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 50% RH. The mean values of at least ten measurements for every fiber were calculated.

A two-probe setup with a Keithley 2001 and a DC power supply (ELV PS 7000) was used to obtain the I - V curves while the specimens were kept in a desiccator with silica gel to avoid the influence of moisture.

The Raman spectra have been recorded using the confocal Raman microscope alpha 300 R (WITec GmbH, Ulm, Germany) equipped with a laser with an excitation wavelength of 532 nm. The samples were analyzed with a 20 \times objective and an integration time of 0.5 s. The laser power was 1 mW. To improve the signal-to-noise ratio, 200 accumulations were done. For a better comparison, each spectrum has been normalized to the highest peak in the range of 800 to 2000 cm^{-1} .

2.4 Characterization of Sensing Abilities

To investigate the piezoresistive effect, the electrical resistance was recorded as the specimen underwent uniaxial tensile or cyclic loading using the FAVIGRAPH semiautomatic equipment (Textechno Company, Germany) equipped with a 1 N load cell. A Keithley 2001 multimeter having a measurement range from 10^{-6} to $10^9 \Omega$ was used to monitor the electrical resistance change of the specimens. The cyclic loading and unloading tension tests were conducted with an initial gauge length of 30 mm, a cross-head velocity of 0.2 mm/min and a strain amplitude of 3%. The specimen was fixed between two clamps coated with conductive silver paste (Acheson Silver DAG 1415M, Plano GmbH, Wetzlar, Germany) serving as electrodes. Simultaneous resistance, strain and load measurements were integrated with the time scale in a customized data acquisition package, TestPoint 2.0.

The vapor sensing behavior was investigated by recording the resistance change of samples during cyclic flows of diluted organic vapor and dry air according to [8,9]. The dimension of the part exposed to the target analyte is the same (length: 10 mm). The temperature of the bubbler evaporation system was set to 25 °C if not stated otherwise. Common organic solvents, such as methanol, ethanol, acetone, chloroform and tetrahydrofuran (THF), were used to produce vapors for the target analytes, respectively.

The liquid sensing behavior was investigated by recording the resistance change of samples during cyclic immersion and drying step according to [8,9]. The immersion (wetting) was carried out under controlled temperatures using a heating/cooling bath. For the drying step the test fixture was lifted up and the remaining solvent drops were wiped off by tissue carefully. The drying took place in air at 23 °C and 50% RH. The samples were tested in distilled water and NaCl aqueous solution, respectively.

In order to compare the sensing properties of specimens independently of their initial resistance, the sensor response was normalized according to Equation (1):

$$R_{rel} = (R_t - R_0)/R_0 \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Here, R_0 is the initial resistance of the specimen; R_t is the transient resistance upon external stimuli (tensile loading for stress/strain sensing, exposure to liquids or vapors).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The Formation of Electrically Conducting CNT Networks on Cellulose Fiber Surfaces

The cellulose fibers used in this work are regenerated by the viscose process. The deposition of MWCNTs onto cellulose fibers shows that the color of cellulose fibers turned from white to light gray or black depending on the treatment condition. As the SEM images show (Figure 1) [11], the interconnected CNT networks were formed on cellulose fiber surfaces after dip coating in the prepared CNT dispersions. This process is efficient for both cellulose monofilament fibers and multifilament fibers to be modified with CNTs. Due to the hygroscopic nature of cellulose (a large amount of hydroxyl groups), the coating of CNTs on the cellulose fiber surfaces was much more efficient than their coating on a glass fiber surface, which was performed in our previous work [10].

Once the CNT-coated cellulose fibers were dried, it was impossible to remove the CNTs coated from the fibers by exposure to solvents, heat or a combination of both. This could be a result of the efficient interaction of carbon nanotubes with cellulose-based materials. In order to study the interaction between the CNTs and the cellulose fiber surface, Raman spectra of the pristine MWCNTs, cellulose fibers and CNT-coated cellulose fibers were recorded. As the results, up-shifts in both D-band (from 1337 to 1351 cm^{-1}) and G-band (from 1577 to 1591 cm^{-1}) positions could be observed in the spectrum of CNT-coated cellulose fibers [11,12]. These shifts suggest that strong non-covalent interactions, such as hydrogen bonds between cellulose fiber and CNTs, were created. This might be the reason for the favourable CNT-cellulose interfacial bonding of CNT-coated cellulose fibers. Additionally, the flexibility of the CNTs allows them to conform to the surface of the cellulose fibers.

As one of the important fundamental properties, the mechanical properties of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers has no significant change compared with that of the original cellulose fibers. For their uniform structure and controllable dimension, mechanical and other properties are stable and can be

repeated well for CNT-coated viscose fibers, as well as the original ones. Even though the cellulose fibers became slightly stiffer after being coated with CNTs, they are still very flexible, which is important for the wearability of electronic fabrics or other applications.

The measured resistance, as length normalized resistance, R_L , of the single CNT-coated cellulose fiber could be in the range of 50–200,000 k Ω /cm, according to the CNT dispersions used and the number of dipping repetitions [8]. In order to reflect the quasi-one-dimensional nature of the fibers, we use length normalized resistance R_L instead of resistivity for comparison. It was proved that the conductivity of the CNT–cellulose fibers increases with increasing of CNT content in dispersions and number of dipping repetitions, respectively. This is because of the better percolation of the deposited CNTs could be obtained when more dipping repetitions or higher CNT content dispersions used in dip coating. In principle, it would be true that a threshold or saturation value of electrical properties could be reached with extensive overlapping CNT networks after a high number of dipping repetitions or using dispersions with high CNT content. Thus, cellulose-based fibers with controllable electrical conductivities while preserving original physical properties were prepared through a simple process of dip coating.

The current–voltage (I – V) characteristics of a single CNT-coated cellulose fiber were also investigated. Same as that of CNT-coated glass fiber [10], they are linear over a wide range of voltages (0–30 V), suggesting ideal Ohmic contacts between nanotubes as well as electrodes.

Figure 1: SEM images of the surface of CNT-coated cellulose fiber (a, c, d) by a 0.5 wt% MWCNT dispersion; (a) monofilament cellulose fiber; (c) multifilament cellulose fibers; (d) well-formed MWCNT networks on the fiber surface; and (b) the favourable CNT–cellulose interfacial bonding.

3.2 CNT-Coated Cellulose Fibers as Stress/Strain Sensors

With well-formed CNT networks coated on the surface, the modified cellulose fibers provide the possibility to serve as smart fibers, such as sensing external stimuli. In this part, the piezoresistivity for strain sensing is investigated for CNT-coated cellulose fibers. Figure 2 shows the correlation of electrical resistance changes, mechanical stress and strain of CNT-coated cellulose fibers under stress up to fracture. At very low strains (below $\epsilon \approx 0.2\%$), the observed constant electrical resistance suggests that the change in the CNT network shape can be neglected. With increasing strain (ϵ), the relative electrical resistance change (R_{rel}) of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers increases monotonously and linearly, almost without noise. This linear strain-dependent electrical resistance keeps even after the yield and until the final fracture [11].

Figure 2: The relative electrical resistance change (R_{rel}) versus strain for CNT-coated cellulose fiber.

The strain sensing of CNT-coated cellulose fibers is mainly due to the piezoresistivity of the electrically-conductive network of carbon nanotubes on the cellulose fibers. When the CNT network is altered by mechanical deformation, a change in the resistivity occurs. In our case, the locally high concentration of CNTs on our cellulose fiber surface can be considered as overlapping at the contact locations, rather than being arranged in an end-to-end configuration. Thus, the percolation-based scaling rule, which accounts for the effects of the network geometry change, might be the dominant phenomenon, leading to the linear resistance change as a function of strain. The tunneling resistance effect might not play a major role here [11]. According to the linear correlation in Figure 2, the GF value for this CNT-coated cellulose fiber is 14.5, which is much higher than that of metal alloys used for conventional foil gages (0.74–5.1). It is noted that the linear correlation between fractional resistance and strain for this CNT-coated cellulose fiber is up to 18% strain until the final fracture. This linear strain range is much larger than that of CNT-coated jute fiber (about 1.5% strain) and other CNT/polymer composites (below 3% strain). For our CNT-coated cellulose fibers, furthermore, the R_{rel} value before the final fracture can be up to 200%–400%, which is much higher than that of most reported CNT-based materials. These results indicate that our CNT-coated cellulose fibers are more efficient and sensitive for use as stress/strain sensors.

Additionally, this unique piezoresistive behavior of CNT-coated cellulose fiber exhibits good reversibility and repeatability [11]. These impressive characteristics indicate that our CNT-coated cellulose fibers are perfect for use as strain sensors. Thus, these sensory fibers can be woven together with other fibers for smart textiles and wearable technology, for example to be used to monitor the motion of muscles and limbs for rehabilitative and telemedicine applications. Moreover, our CNT-coated cellulose fibers can be used as integrated sensors or surface-mounted strain gauges to monitor crack initiation/propagation and strain/stress in different composite structures.

3.3 CNT-Coated Cellulose Fibers as Vapor Sensors

Due to their large adsorption capacity and the change of electrical resistance upon exposure to volatile molecules, CNT networks are good candidates for use as chemical sensors. We then further investigated the sensing ability of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers to volatile organic compounds (VOCs). In order to describe the vapor sensitivity of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers, the relative electrical resistance change (R_{rel}) of these exposed to gas pulses of solvent vapors was recorded as a function of time. Figure 3a shows the resistance response of CNT-coated cellulose fibers to diluted ethanol vapor (7%). Prior to the exposure to the target analyte, the resistance was recorded for 100 s

under dry air to get a stable initial resistance value. Then, CNT-coated cellulose fiber was exposed to five cycles of alternating gas pulses of diluted ethanol vapor and dry air. Clearly, upon exposure to ethanol vapor, an instant sharp increase of resistance was observed. The R_{rel} reaches a value of about 20% after immersion for only 10 s. After 60 s, the R_{rel} value of the fibers reaches 82%. The recovery of the R_{rel} value starts at 3–5 s after injecting of dry air into the detecting chamber due to the time consumption for fully expelling ethanol vapor. Finally, the resistance response curve shows a 15% hysteresis to the initial resistance value due to the remaining solvent vapor on the sample after the ethanol vapor is withdrawn. Therefore, the reversibility of resistance change is evaluated starting from the second cycle. The fiber exhibits fast and reproducible responsiveness as characterized by the significant increase in R_{rel} of about 80%, indicating its good sensing ability of ethanol vapor.

It should be noted that the CNT-coated cellulose fibers exhibit a positive vapor coefficient for ethanol and acetone vapors, which is also found in other CNT-based sensory materials for vapor sensing. In our cases, it can be deduced that the resistance responses of CNT-coated cellulose fibers for VOC can be attributed to the adsorption of VOC molecules by both the cellulose fiber and the CNT networks. Compared to the CNT-based composites, furthermore, the unique distribution of CNT networks on the fiber surface provides a large, well-defined surface area and the capacity to make contact more directly and efficiently with analytes, leading to the rapid response and high sensitivity for CNT-coated cellulose fibers as vapor sensors.

Figure 3: Typical resistance response (R_{rel}) of CNT-coated cellulose fiber to vapors: (a) ethanol vapour (7%) for five cycles; (b) solvent vapors (saturated vapor concentration at 25 °C) for 60 s.

Figure 3b shows the relative resistance response (R_{rel}) of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers after exposure to various solvent vapors (saturated vapor concentration at 25 °C) for 60 s. For the different effects on the electrical resistance of nanotubes, as well as the swelling of cellulose fiber by adsorption of different VOC molecules, the resistance response of the fibers to these vapors is different. Thus, it is possible to monitor different vapors using our modified fibers by evaluation of their electrical resistance response.

3.3 CNT-Coated Cellulose Fibers as Liquid Water Sensors

The liquid sensitivity of these CNT-coated cellulose fibers was also investigated. For CNT-coated cellulose fibers ($R_L = 179 \text{ k}\Omega/\text{cm}$), the R_{rel} increases very rapidly and reaches a very high value of 100% after immersion in water only 5 s [8]. These fast and reliable responses indicate that the CNT-cellulose fibers are very sensitive to liquid water. During the following time, the increase of R_{rel} is relatively slow and reaches about 115% after 30 s of immersion. Obviously, the CNT-cellulose fibers exhibit a positive liquid coefficient, which is similar to that for vapors mentioned above.

As described above, the coated CNTs on cellulose fiber surface could be considered as extensive nanotube overlapping networks. It is deduced that the resistance responses of CNT-coated cellulose fibers on water could be attributed to the adsorption of water molecules by both, cellulose fiber (ΔR_S)

and CNT layers (ΔR_A). It can be observed that the highly hygroscopic swelling of the cellulose fiber has already occurred in the initial 2-5 s, with the diameter of the fiber increasing from about 20.8 μm to 26.5 μm [8]. This enlargement of fiber volume caused by the swelling increases the nanotube-nanotube distance of neighbored CNTs above the tunnelling or hopping distances, leading to the sharp increase of the resistance. On the other hand, the adsorbed water molecules on the surface of CNTs also affect the electrical resistance. Compared with that of liquid water sensing for CNT-coated glass fibers, furthermore, the swelling of cellulose fibers exposed to water (ΔR_S) is proved to be the dominant mechanism, while ΔR_A has no contribution to the positive liquid coefficient [8].

It is noted that, during the following 60 s for the drying of the fibers in air at ambient conditions, the R_{rel} value decreases to the same level as that of initial baseline ($R_{\text{rel}} = 0$). It indicates the CNT-coated cellulose fibers have a good recovery as water sensors. That is, the structure and properties of cellulose fibers remain unchangeable after the wetting/drying cycle. This feature is mainly due to that cellulose does not dissolve but only swells in water. On the other hand, it also demonstrates there exists favourable CNT-cellulose interfacial bonding, which results in the good stability of the materials. Compared with that of sensory CPCs for liquid sensing, the usual response/recover time of our MWNT-cellulose fibers are much shorter, which are only several/tens of seconds. Moreover, the response signals are quite stable and reproducible under cyclic wetting and drying process. All the R_{rel} values increase (or decrease) almost to the same level during the wetting (or drying) process. It indicates their good repeatability [8]. Thus, our CNT-coated cellulose fibers are not only sensitive, but also well reversible and reproducible for water sensing.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of CNT-coated cellulose fibers as simple water leak alarm.

For CNT-coated cellulose fibers with higher resistivity (such as 621 $\text{k}\Omega/\text{cm}$ and 1160 $\text{k}\Omega/\text{cm}$), the amplitudes of their responses are much larger than that mentioned above. That is, the sensitivity increases with the increase of resistivity of materials. This character is in good agreement with the percolation theory, same as CNT-cellulose composites for liquid sensing. Driven by the highly hygroscopic swelling of cellulose fiber, the conductive CNT networks on the cellulose fiber surface tend to readily disconnect at less dense nanotube network structure. It further confirms that the ΔR_S is the dominant phenomenon for the high sensitivity of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers to water. Interestingly, for CNT-coated cellulose fibers with relatively high resistivity such as 13.5 $\text{M}\Omega/\text{cm}$, an alternative function—the electrochemical “switch” is found, where the electrical signals turn ON and OFF states with a variation of wetting and drying process [8]. The conversion of ON-OFF state is also quite stable and reproducible during the cyclic wetting and drying process. Therefore, the swelling-shrinking of CNT-coated cellulose fibers during wetting-drying cycle results in the efficient “break-junction” (disconnection-connection of CNT network) mechanism. This impressive water sensing properties of CNT-coated cellulose fibers provides a simple and unique way to fabricate the electrochemical “sensor” or “switch”, which have the potential to be used in a wide range of practical applications, such as water leak alarm (Figure 4).

Usually, water found in natural environment or used in our ordinary life contains many other substances, including some ions which will increase the conductivity of the water. What is the influence of the ions on the sensitivity of CNT-coated cellulose fibers to such water might also attract much attention. Here, the sensing behavior of CNT-coated cellulose fibers to electrolyte solution (1 % NaCl aqueous solution) was investigated. Similarly, they exhibit a rapid increase in resistivity with increasing immersion time when immersed in NaCl aqueous solution, as well as reversible and

reproducible sensing behaviour in the following drying process and repeated cycles [8]. Furthermore, there is no obvious change for the amplitude of the response compared with that of distilled water. This character of the CNT-coated cellulose fibers further broadens the field of practical applications. For example, it is possible to monitor the sweating from human body by using our CNT-coated cellulose fibers in smart textiles.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Electrically conductive CNT-coated cellulose fibers were been prepared through a simple and efficient way by dip coating. Strong non-covalent interactions between the cellulose fiber and CNTs were created, leading to favorable CNT-cellulose interfacial bonding. The uniformly formed CNT networks on the surfaces of fibers not only provided good conductivity to the modified fibers, but also led to excellent sensing abilities to external stimuli, in the combination with the intrinsic physical and chemical features of cellulose fiber. As stress/strain sensors, these CNT-coated cellulose fibers exhibited a highly linear and repeatable electrical resistance correlation to tensile strain, with good reversibility and repeatability. As chemical vapor sensors, our fibers exhibit a simple, sensitive and selective sensing ability for chemical vapors, indicating their potential to be designed as a new type of electronic nose (e-nose) for VOCs and other gases. As liquid sensors, they are demonstrated to be used as highly sensitive, well reversible and reproducible sensor for water, with a sensitivity of 100 - 8000%. And the CNT-coated fibers can even serve as simple and efficient electrochemical water “switches”. Moreover, these functional fibers exhibited good sensibility to aqueous electrolytes solution.

Figure 5: Photograph and microstructure of various CNT-integrated cellulose materials produced: CNT/cellulose composites (films and aerogels) and CNT-coated cellulose fibers.

Additionally, we have developed a novel green process to fabricate CNT/cellulose composites (Figure 5) by dissolving cellulose and dispersing CNTs homogeneously in aqueous alkaline/urea solution [12-14]. The network formation of the CNTs in cellulose matrix not only introduced good conductivity to the materials, but also led to the impressive multifunctional sensing abilities. By combination the features of both cellulose and CNTs, therefore, there are great opportunities to develop various smart and functional materials based on cellulose and CNTs, including one-dimension (1D, such as fibers), two-dimension (2D, such as films) and even three-dimension (3D, such as aerogels) materials, which offer potential applications in a wide range of fields.

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